

Research Paper

Sustainable repurposing of grape marc: Potential for bio-based innovations

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ABSTRACT

There is increasing interest in repurposing by-products and residues from agricultural and agri-food industries, supporting environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Wineries and distilleries, an important segment of EU agriculture, generate substantial levels of waste annually with grape marc, a significant by-product of these industries, representing both an environmental challenge and an untapped resource. To achieve the sector's 2050 zero-waste vision, innovative waste management strategies are crucial. This review aims to explore the potential of grape marc as a natural source of high-value compounds and its conversion into a portfolio of high-value added bio-based products. The review discusses grape marc generation and the associated waste management challenges within the wine and distillery industries. It highlights innovative biological, thermal, and chemical conversion strategies for turning grape marc into high-value products. Additionally, it provides an overview of the main components of grape marc and explores its wide range of alternative applications, with particular emphasis placed on nutraceuticals, functional food and feed, biofuels, biomaterials, and agricultural amendments. In addition, the study highlights the integration of grape marc into a fungal-based biorefinery system, as promising upcycling strategy to drive innovation in the development of bio-based products, enabling a transformative waste-to-resource pathway. The findings support the advancement of innovative and feasible valorization models, contributing to sustainable waste management practices within circular economy framework.

1. Introduction

Today, the food and beverage sectors face critical challenges—from climate change to significant food loss and waste—posing serious threats to global food security and sustainability. The European Union (EU) aims for climate neutrality by 2050, focusing on Circular Economy principles (European Commission, 2020) and eco-innovation strategies to boost sustainability. The sustainable consumption and production can become more attainable by encouraging the development of alternative technologies, and changing the linear model in favor of new strategies that are more efficient and sustainable (Jamaludin et al., 2022).

The EU is the world's largest producer, consumer and exporter of wine (Šajin, 2023). Indeed, the European wine sector is remarkably sensitive to the issue of sustainability in general and the environmental impact of production in particular. The growing awareness of food and winery waste has been reflected in the (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2018) requiring member states to establish waste prevention programs, and in the European Parliament resolution (2011/2175(INI)) (Publications Office of the European

Union, 2012), as initiatives to avoid waste and make food chains more efficient. The Common Agricultural Policy (European Commission, 2023) and the EU wine policy improve the response of EU ambitious environmental and social objectives, including sustainable production and reduction of waste. The EU engages strongly with resource-efficiency narratives, with key attention to terms relating to recovery activities and waste management (Calisto Friant et al., 2021).

In this context, the generation of grape marc biomass by wineries and distilleries represents a current drawback of the utilization in many EU countries, whilst the lack of proper pragmatic procedures for its valorization is considered a global issue. Considering the novel legislation about recycling and sustainability, exploitation of winery underutilized resources has drawn attention for creation of valuable products and ingredients. Moreover, repurposing of grape marc represents an opportunity for economic gain, improved soil health and positive environmental outcomes, if appropriately processed (Jones et al., 2020). To manage sustainably the grape marc, green processes and emerging techniques are being proposed (Ilyas et al., 2021; Perra et al., 2022).

Recent studies have increasingly focused on extraction of bioactive

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molecules (Liu et al., 2025; Nirmal et al., 2025) and few studies have explored the biorefinery approaches (Cebrián et al., 2024). Grape marc, as a source of bioactive compounds, is particularly suitable for responding to the current biomedical and technological demands. Numerous techno-economic studies highlight the economic and environmental benefits of using grape marc for value-added products and energy (Muhlack et al., 2018). In addition, integrated strategies have been explored for the valorization of grape marc to obtain a wide range of valuable compounds as biomaterials, bioplastics, biofertilisers, bioenergy, bioactive compounds, and food or feed ingredients (Bharathiraja et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2022; Taifouris et al., 2023). Such approaches, could drive the transition towards a circular economy by turning waste into valuable bio-based products, fostering innovation, enhancing environmental sustainability and resource efficiency, also creating new economic opportunities (Abreu et al., 2024).

Despite ongoing efforts, the vast quantities of grape marc generated annually, along with limited processing facilities and economically feasible models, continue to hinder its effective utilization. This review aims to contribute with a comprehensive analysis of grape marc’s versatility, highlighting cutting-edge applications of this residue while prioritizing the tree pillars of sustainability. By exploring the grape marc potential as a rich source of high-value compounds, and its conversion into a portfolio of bio-based products, this study covers opportunities beyond its traditional utilization. In addition, it outlines recent

valorization trends and transformative strategies that support the creation of diverse, value-added solutions. Applications span food and feed, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, energy, construction, and soil conditioning, aligning strongly with circular economy principles. Furthermore, this study suggests future research avenues that advance biotechnological applications, by including grape marc in a fungi-based biorefinery system. This upcycling strategy for grape marc enables the eco-efficient production of protein-rich biomass, enzymes, and bioactive compounds, supporting EU zero-waste targets and unlocking cost-effective, sustainable solutions for multiple sectors. This highlights a practical, forward-looking path for both innovation and investment in circular bioeconomy markets, improve waste management, contribute to sustainable food systems and circular bioeconomy.

2. An overview of the distilleries, grape and wine, production and the generated grape marc

The wine industry is a significant sector globally, both in terms of raw material processing and economic production within the food and beverage industries. Wine is produced by fermentation of grapes, one of the most extensively cultivated crops in the world, with global production reaching 80.1 million tones (Mtons) of fresh grape. Out of this total, according to data from the Organisation Internationale de la Vigne et du Vin, almost 50 % (37.3 Mtons) is used for “pressed grapes” notably

Fig. 1. Diagram of the vinification process for white and red wines. Red circles highlight the main by-products generated during processing.

for the production of wine (34.1 Mtons) and for the production of musts and juices (3.2 Mtons), and the other 50 % destined as table grapes and raisins (OIV, 2024).

In 2023, the global vineyard surface area was approximately 7.2 million hectares (Mha), supporting a worldwide wine production of 237 million hectoliters (Mhl). Europe was the leading wine producer, with a vineyard area of about 3.3 Mha and a vinified production of around 144.5 Mhl. Within the EU, Spain, France, and Italy were the top three producers, accounting for 87 % of total EU production and 52 % of global output. Their vineyard areas measured 945, 792, and 720 kha, respectively, with wine production of 35.0, 46.6, and 43.2 Mhl (OIV, 2024).

One of the key distinctions in winemaking is between white and red wine production (Fig. 1). Stalks are typically removed early in the winemaking process through destemming, the remaining grape solids—namely skins and seeds—are separated via pressing before alcoholic fermentation in white winemaking.

In contrast, for red wines, these solids remain during fermentation and maceration and are only removed afterward through pressing. This pressing step produces a solid by-product known as grape pomace or grape marc, which is typically sent to distilleries for further processing. At the distillery, the marc from white grapes (unfermented) is first stored to undergo fermentation before being distilled to extract ethanol. Red grape marcs are treated similarly, but usually without the fermentation step at the distillery, as they already contain ethanol.

In the Table 1 are presented data on processed grape and produced wine globally in Europe and in the three leading European countries—Italy, France, and Spain. To produce a 0.75 L bottle of wine, 1.2–1.3 kg of grapes are needed. These numbers correspond to a wine yield of 65 to 75 %, depending on the wine type and on the processing method. Wine production requires a substantial investment of resources, including water, fertilizers, and organic amendments. At the same time, it generates high amounts of oenological by-products. Grape marc, also known as grape bagasse or grape pomace represents up to 60 % of the wine solid wastes and being generally 20–30 % of the processed grapes (Nanni et al., 2021; Niculescu and Ionete, 2023).

Based on processed grape and wine production data (OIV, 2024) and depending on grape variety and vinification method, it is estimated that approximately 7.58–11.3 Mtons of grape marc are generated globally each year. Within Europe, annual grape marc production is estimated at 4.70–7.05 Mtons, while for the three main wine-producing countries—Italy, France, and Spain—the combined total is estimated at 4.0–6.0 Mtons per year in 2023 (Table 1).

In the EU, distillation by authorized distillers of wine by-products like grape marc and lees is a mandatory practice (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2013), established to help prevent excessive grape pressing, support environmental sustainability, and to contribute to the production of distilled spirits. In 2023, the European Union (EU) produced about 68.3 million hectoliters of agricultural alcohol, with wine and wine by-products accounting for around 4 % of the total production, approximately 2.73 million hectoliters. While cereals and sugar by-products are the dominant feedstocks for alcohol production, grape marc remains a significant raw material for producing high-ethanol spirits (AssoDistil, 2024).

The seasonal nature of winemaking leads to high concentrations of GM waste. The improper disposal of grape marc as a waste can

contribute to environmental concerns due to its high organic carbon content (41.2–54.9 %) (del Contreras et al., 2022; Muhlack et al., 2018; Saha et al., 2020; Tamelová et al., 2021). GM may exert phytotoxic effects if applied to crops or wetlands and can impact wildlife. Because of the high moisture, sugar, and temperature attract pests that may spread nearby populations or surrounding crops (El Achkar et al., 2016). In addition, can cause water pollution, odors, and oxygen depletion in soil and water, harming local ecosystems (Beres et al., 2017). GM's nutrient leakage and antimicrobial properties further endanger local flora and fauna (Dwyer et al., 2014). Furthermore, its high phenolic and organic acid content lowers pH levels, resists degradation (Nayak et al., 2018).

GM has a high chemical oxygen demand 223–1293 g O₂/kg (El Achkar et al., 2016; Perra et al., 2022). Given the carbon footprint about 900 kg CO₂-eq/tones of wastes (Litskas et al., 2020), the disposal of GM could result more than 4.7 Mtons in an estimated CO₂ emission (Iuga and Mironeasa, 2020). Reducing GM environmental footprint is critical for sustainability and helps minimize ecological and resource-related impacts.

3. Composition of grape marc and its potential as a bio-resource

GM is a highly variable by-product, and its composition, quality, and quantity are influenced by various factors, including climate, viticultural practices, grape variety and maturity, sanitary conditions, soil characteristics, winemaking methods and equipment, winery size, geographic origin, and vintage (Abouelenein et al., 2023; Niculescu and Ionete, 2023; Perra et al., 2022). Vinification techniques further affect the physico-chemical properties of GM, determining its suitability for specific valorization pathways. The valorization of GM for industrial applications is closely linked to its complex chemical composition (Bordiga et al., 2019), and due to its variability, thorough GM characterization is essential.

Tables 2 presents the average composition of fresh and dried GM (both red and white), providing a detailed overview based on existing literature data. Fresh GM has high moisture content, ranging from 20.6 % to 82 % depending on the degree of pressing, on the grape variety and ripeness (Spinei and Oroian, 2021). The high moisture level make it perishable, and to extend its shelf life and preserve its properties, drying might be crucial (Carmona-Jiménez et al., 2018), though it may induce biochemical changes in the material (Tseng and Zhao, 2013). GM contains sugar, primarily glucose (0.2–26.3 %) and fructose (0.4–8.91 %). Unfermented GM can contain up to 38 % glucose and fructose (dry weight basis) (Hixson et al., 2014). Conversely, fermented GM contains ethanol and varying amounts of residual sugars, depending on the winemaking process (Hungria et al., 2021). For example, marc from red sparkling wine production retains 18–30 % residual sugars, while still red wine production yields as little as 1 % glucose and fructose (dry weight) (Hixson et al., 2014; Muhlack et al., 2018).

GM is a complex substrate rich in macromolecules such as proteins (3.6–14.4 %), fat (1–15.3 %) and carbohydrates (3–13.9 %). Pectin, the primary polymer-type constituent in cell walls, accounts for 37%–54 % of cell wall polysaccharides, making GM a significant pectin source after citrus and apple pomaces, with potential applications in the food industry (e.g., as a texture/rheology additive and in edible films). Cellulose is the second most abundant cell wall polysaccharide in GM, while hemicellulose is an important source of fiber. In addition, GM contains high levels of lignin (11–32.5 %). Dietary fiber, primarily consists of cell wall polysaccharides and lignin and constitutes 17–88.7 %, where red GM is richer in fiber than white GM. The total ash in GM ranges from 0.55 to 13.3 %. The most abundant element in GM is carbon (41.2–54.9 %), followed by oxygen (32.7–38.4 %), hydrogen (5.53–9.28 %), and nitrogen (0.54–3.0 %).

Additionally, GM is an excellent source of bioactive compounds (11.2–168.4 mg gallic acid equivalent/g) (Abouelenein et al., 2023; Mohamed Ahmed et al., 2020; Natolino et al., 2024; Radulescu et al., 2024; Spinei and Oroian, 2021) particularly rich in anthocyanins

Table 1

Global, European and data from Italy-France-Spain production of grapes, wine, and generated GM (values in 10⁶ tones).

	Processed grapes ^a	Produced wine	Grape marc
World	37.3	23.5	7.58–11.3
Europe	23.5	14.3	4.70–7.05
Italy-France-Spain	20.0	12.4	4.0–6.0

^a considered the grapes used for wine production (Adapted from OIV (2024)).

Table 2
Main composition of fresh and dried GM (values are expressed on dry matter).

Main components	Fresh GM	Reference	Dried GM	Reference
Moisture %	20.6–82	(Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Mohamed Ahmed et al., 2020; Perra et al., 2022)	5.5–7.8	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019; Nayak et al., 2018; Ramos and Ferreira, 2022; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Organic matter %	82.7–95.9	(Bordiga et al., 2019; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022)		
Total Solids %	37.1–45.1	(El Achkar et al., 2016; Perra et al., 2022)		
Volatile matter %	33.4–87.4	(El Achkar et al., 2016; Hungría et al., 2021; Perra et al., 2022)	65.7–72.4	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019; Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Fixed carbon %	12.5–31.1	(Hungría et al., 2021)	24.4–27.3	(Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Carbon (C) %	41.2–54.9	(Contreras et al., 2022; Muhlack et al., 2018; Saha et al., 2020; Tamelová et al., 2021)	50.8–51.5	(Contreras et al., 2022; Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Nitrogen (N) %	0.54–3.0	(Saha et al., 2020; Tamelová et al., 2021)	1.18–2.74	(Contreras et al., 2022; Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Hydrogen (H) %	5.4–9.28	(Contreras et al., 2022; Muhlack et al., 2018; Saha et al., 2020)	5.53–6.40	(Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Oxygen (O) %	32.7–32.9	(Contreras et al., 2022; Saha et al., 2020; Tamelová et al., 2021)	33.6–38.4	(Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
pH	3.3–5.4	(Bender et al., 2020; Bustamante et al., 2008; Fríncu et al., 2023; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Hungría et al., 2021; Lafka et al., 2007; Perra et al., 2022)		
Total ash %	0.55–13.3	(Contreras et al., 2022; Mohamed Ahmed et al., 2020; Muhlack et al., 2018; Perra et al., 2022; Saha et al., 2020; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)	3.25–10.4	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019; Nayak et al., 2018; Ramos and Ferreira, 2022)
Crude protein %	3.6–14.4	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Bender et al., 2020; Contreras et al., 2022; Fríncu et al., 2023; Hungría et al., 2021; Mohamed Ahmed et al., 2020; Mora-Garrido et al., 2022; Perra et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2020; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	9.98–10.3	(Nayak et al., 2018; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Crude fat %	1–13.9	(Antonić et al., 2020; Perra et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	9.82–15.3	(Nayak et al., 2018; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Total carbohydrates %	3–13.9	(Abouelenein et al., 2023)		
Crude fiber %	14.7–22.3	(Lo Curto, 2001)	32.1–51.8	(Mohamed Ahmed et al., 2020)
Total dietary fiber %	17–88.7	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Antonić et al., 2020; Perra et al., 2022; Tseng and Zhao, 2013)	60.1	(Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Cellulose %	7–75	(Bender et al., 2020; Hungría et al., 2021; Niculescu and Ionete, 2023; Perra et al., 2022)		
Hemicellulose %	6–22	(Bender et al., 2020; Perra et al., 2022)		
Lignin %	11–32.5	(Bender et al., 2020; Hungría et al., 2021; Perra et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2020)	30.2	(Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Pectin %	3.68	(Tseng and Zhao, 2013)		
Glucose %	0.2–26.3	(Antonić et al., 2020; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	5.4	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)
Fructose %	0.4–8.91	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Antonić et al., 2020; Spinei and Oroian, 2021; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)		
Calcium (Ca) mg/kg	500–10335	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021; Suescun-Ospina et al., 2023)	6220	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019)
Potassium (K) mg/kg	11,800–37,900	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	6770	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019)
Phosphorus (P) mg/kg	40–31570	(Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	2570	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019)
Magnesium (Mg) mg/kg	800–6440	(Abouelenein et al., 2023; Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	890	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019)
Manganese (Mn) mg/kg	<0.2–13560	(Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)		
Iron (Fe) mg/kg	110	(Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)	110	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2019)
Copper (Cu) mg/kg	1.30–1300	(Antonić et al., 2020; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022; Hungría et al., 2021; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)		
Zinc (Zn) mg/kg	5.39–22540	(Antonić et al., 2020; Hungría et al., 2021; Spinei and Oroian, 2021)		

(17.6–69 mg/g) (Natolino et al., 2024; Radulescu et al., 2024) and flavonoids (25.6–62.3 mg quercetin equivalent/g) (Ianni and Martino, 2020). These compound contribute to strong antioxidant properties (Negro et al., 2021).

In summary, the complex chemical composition makes GM a valuable source for recovering high-value compounds. This potential supports the development of eco-efficient, value-added products aligned with sustainability and circular bioeconomy goals.

4. Multifaceted approaches for grape marc valorization

4.1. Grape marc repurposing

Recently, pressure has risen within the wine industry to implement plans for the feasible green disposal or valorization of GM (Muhlack et al., 2018). To analyze the association between grape marc (GM) and its repurposing potential, a text mining approach was employed using VOSviewer version 1.6.20 for bibliometric analysis (van Eck and Waltman, 2010). The search resulted in 3,714 documents, based on keywords selected related to GM valorization, extraction, fermentation, composting, anaerobic digestion, thermal treatments, enzymatic hydrolysis, and its use in functional food, animal feed, and bioenergy production. A

2024; Hixson et al., 2018). However, drawbacks include limited animal weight gain and the potential negative effects on digestion due to the high content of lignified fibers and secondary metabolites (e.g., tannins and anthocyanins) (Perra et al., 2022).

4.2.3. Spirits

The main exploitation strategy for grape marc remains distillation to produce spirits, which is widely practiced in Italy (100 %), France (90 %), and Spain (30–60 %) (Nanni et al., 2021). In the EU, distillation by authorized distillers of wine by-products like grape marc and lees is a mandatory practice, established to help prevent excessive grape pressing, support environmental sustainability, and to contribute to the production of distilled spirits. GM can only be distilled (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2013), into alcohol, spirits, or piquette, not used for wine or other beverage intended for human consumption, and 44 categories of spirit drinks, including GM spirit are defined (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024).

Distillation has long been a traditional use of GM, giving rise to spirits with cultural and economic value, such as Grappa in Italy, Zivania in Cyprus, Eaux de Vie de Marc in France, Bagaçeira in Portugal, Orujo in Spain, and Tsipouro/Tsikoudia in Greece (Cisneros-Yupanqui et al., 2023; Giannetti et al., 2019; Kokoti et al., 2023; Tsapou et al., 2024). GM, especially those with higher sugar content, might be considered a by-product with applications in (bio)ethanol production with a theoretical yield of 0.21–0.40 L/kg biomass, depending on the wine type (del Contreras et al., 2022). Another use of GM is the production of “wine alcohol” for valorized distilled spirits, liquors, and liqueurs, and piquette (Watrelet and Hollis, 2024). However, distillation involves resource use, significant costs, and CO₂ emissions. The distillation process also generates spent grape marc, which can be further processed for various applications.

4.3. Advancements in grape marc valorization

Alternative uses of GM include (bio)fertilizers, bioethanol, organic acids (tartaric, malic, citric), biofuels, bioenergy, biochar, biogas, biocomposites, biomethane, and biosurfactants. Recently, GM has gained attraction in the food sector as a source of dietary fiber, isolated polysaccharides, functional ingredients, enzymes, flavors, pigments, nutraceuticals, antioxidants, mycelium, single-cell proteins, and food packaging. These applications span various industries, including agriculture, viticulture, food and wine production, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, chemicals, and energy.

4.3.1. Valorization of GM by biological conversion processes

4.3.1.1. Composting and vermicomposting. Composting and vermicomposting are well-established processes for the biological stabilization of solid organic wastes. These processes have also been successfully applied to process distillery residues from the wine sector, including both fresh and spent grape marc (Echeverría-Vega et al., 2024; Gabur et al., 2024; Gómez et al., 2024; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2023, 2022, 2020; Hanc et al., 2019; Nogales et al., 2020). This processing leads to a reduction of the C:N ratio, conductivity, and phytotoxicity, while increasing the nutrient content of the humic materials and pH. Compost derived from winery wastes has been shown to be of good quality and can be used in the vineyards (Kokkonen et al., 2024). An innovative compost combining zeolite and winery wastes was tested against commercial compost, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving vineyard soil quality and fertility by enhancing available water content, nutrient retention, carbon sequestration, and biological activity (Doni et al., 2024).

Composted and vermicomposted hydrolyzed and spent GM can be used as a plant substrate and fertilizer (Villena et al., 2018).

Vermicomposting, in particular, has been effective in transforming GM and its distillery effluent into a nutrient-rich, biologically active, and polyphenol-free organic vermicompost (Gómez-Brandón et al., 2021). The GM pretreated with *Ulocladium botrytis* was suggested as optimal for vermicomposting, obtaining an organic fertilizer in a short period (Troncozo et al., 2024). However, composting GM alone presents challenges due to its low pH, as the microbes involved in composting prefer a pH closer to neutral.

4.3.1.2. Anaerobic digestion. Anaerobic digestion (AD) is one of the most sustainable technologies for treating and stabilizing organic waste, while also producing biogas and digestate, which can be used as an organic amendment. The biogas produced during the process is mainly composed of CH₄ and CO₂ (typically 70 % and 30 %, respectively, depending on the feedstocks) (Abreu et al., 2024). GM can serve as an important energy source for methane production through AD. The biogas can be purified to biomethane, which can be used as vehicle fuel or to generate electricity and heat (Hungria et al., 2021). A laboratory scale-plant was developed to assess biogas and methane production from the anaerobic digestion of GM. Under mesophilic conditions at the laboratory scale, AD achieved a biodegradability of 51 % (Javier et al., 2019). In addition, the potential of GM for biogas production has been evaluated to support the shift to green energy sources (Bordiga et al., 2019; Labartino et al., 2019). Simulations indicated that up to 94 kWh per ton of GM could be generated, covering up to 45 % of the energy requirements for the winemaking process (Cáceres et al., 2012). However, drawbacks include a carbon footprint of 450 kg CO₂-eq per ton of biowaste, which is nearly equivalent to incineration (Cortés et al., 2020).

4.3.1.3. Fermentation. Fermentation has emerged as a key process due to its ability to convert food waste into a wide range of valuable by-products. Grape marc fermentation has shown potential in the production of microbial polysaccharides, protein, organic acids, and enzymes, and bio-based products, which can be utilized in various biotechnological applications.

Solid-state fermentation (SSF) and submerged fermentation (SmF) using GM as a substrate, with *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Pleurotus pulmonarius* were employed for the production of mushrooms, phenolic compounds, laccase, and endoglucanase. These results demonstrated promising potential for producing valuable food products (Papadaki et al., 2019). The application of GM at different concentrations can influence the total quality index of both whole *P. ostreatus* mushrooms and their extracts (Doroški et al., 2021). The bioconversion of GM using SSF was evaluated for mycelial growth, with potential applications for human food and animal feed using *Pleurotus* spp., *Ganoderma resinaceum* (medicinal fungus), and *Pleurotus cornucopiae* (edible fungus) (Abid et al., 2023). *Agaricus brasiliensis* mycelium produced using GM under SmF and SSF, proved to be an efficient way to produce the biomass with potential for extraction of sterols, antioxidants and fatty acids, to be incorporated in food supplements (Mokochinski et al., 2015). Submerged fermentation (static and shaking) was studied for GM extract bioconversion using *Trametes versicolor*, *Ganoderma lucidum*, and novel edible or medicinal fungi (*Sepedonium* sp., *Phellinus* sp.). The process aimed to produce bioactive protein-polysaccharide mycelium for functional food applications (Kachrimanidou et al., 2023a, 2023b, 2023c).

A novel process was developed for the economical production of a value-added and environmentally friendly biocontrol agent by *Trichoderma viride* using GM (Bai et al., 2008). In addition, recovery of phenolic compounds from GM using *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Trametes versicolor* and *Lentinus edodes* has been successfully achieved under SFF (Šelo et al., 2024, 2023a, 2023b; Yildirim and Sā-Zmen, 2021). The biosynthesis of lignocellulose-degrading enzymes by *Trametes villosa* and *Trichoderma asperellum*, in monocultures and in consortium, was evaluated using GM and wheat bran via SSF (Corrêa et al., 2024). An integrated process for

production citric acid-multi-hydrolytic enzymes (carboxymethyl cellulase, polygalacturonase, amylase, xylanase and acid protease activities) was developed using *Aspergillus niger* by converting GM and wheat bran in mixture under SSF (Selo et al., 2021). Furthermore, promising results for commercial citric acid production were obtained by SSF cultivation of *A. niger* in GM (Başgömez, 2021). Enhanced recovery of phenolic compounds was achieved by cultivation of eleven filamentous fungi (*T. versicolor* TV6, TV8, and AG613, *Trametes gibbosa*, *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*, *Ceriporiopsis subvermispota*, *Pleurotus eryngii*, *Ganoderma lucidum* and *G. resinaceum*, *Humicola grisea*, and *R. oryzae*), in GM, for 15 days via SSF (Selo et al., 2022). Also, grown of white-rot fungus *T. versicolor* for 15 days in GM using laboratory jars and a tray bioreactor under SSF, resulted in improved extractability of bioactive compounds. These conditions, under a complex enzyme system (including lignolytic: laccase and manganese peroxidase, and hydrolytic: xylanase, cellulase, beta-glucosidase, and invertase) could lead to changes in GM's chemical composition, i.e., increased ash, crude protein, and fat content (Selo et al., 2024).

A biorefinery approach was developed by combining GM and soybean hull (1:1 ratio) for the cultivation of *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus oryzae* under SSF, resulting in enhanced production of tannase, α -amylase, cellulase, pectinase, and gallic acid (Cabezudo et al., 2023). Additionally, gallic acid was recovered from *A. niger* cultivated in GM under SmF, leading to the production of relevant industrial enzymes such as tannase, pectinase, and α -amylase (Meini et al., 2020). The recovery of bioactive compounds was achieved by *Aspergillus awamori* cultivation in GM under SSF and in enhanced hydrolytic enzymes production (Teles et al., 2019). *A. niger* and *A. oryzae* fermentation produced GM extracts with enhanced antioxidant and prebiotic activities (Meini et al., 2021). Furthermore, following a biorefinery approach, the fermentation of exhausted grape marc with *R. oryzae* led to an increase in protein content of the final biomass (up to 55 %) (Cebrián et al., 2024). The cultivation of *Aspergillus oryzae* and *Trichoderma reesei* under SSF bioconverted GM into protein-rich animal feed (Zepf and Jin, 2013). *A. niger*-fermented GM was investigated in broiler chicks, and hatched broilers, showing a potential on growth performance, antioxidant capacity, intestinal morphology (Gungor et al., 2021; Madkour et al., 2024; Rybicka et al., 2024). Sheep feeding with GM treated with *Neurospora sitophila* fungus increases the crude protein and rumen-degradable protein and reduces the adverse effects of GM on ruminal kinetics (Hasanzadeh et al., 2023). GM fermentation with *Actinomyces elegans* and *Umbelopsis isabellina* under SSF, enriched with γ -linolenic acid carotenoids and antioxidant potential (Dulf et al., 2020).

New models for the production of biopreservation compounds were developed using GM extracts as a fermentation medium with yeasts (*Candida pyralidae*, *Pichia kluyveri* and *Pichia kluyveri*) (Mewa-Ngongang et al., 2019). In addition, GM was used for the cultivation of commercial yeast, which produced the enzymes polygalacturonase and glucanase, demonstrating potential for GM valorization (Zietsman et al., 2022). Yeast biomass was produced from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* through fed-batch fermentation using fresh GM (Lo Curto, 2001). Using two co-cultures (*P. stipites/A. niger* and *S. cerevisiae/A. niger*) for GM fermentation under SSF, led to significant production of polyphenols, condensed tannins, and flavonoids (Siller-Sánchez et al., 2024). GM has been explored for the potential to produce ethanol due to the significant amounts of fermentable sugars present after pressing grapes. Additionally, bioethanol was obtained by laboratory scale SSF using GM by means of *S. cerevisiae* (Rodríguez et al., 2010). GM has the potential to be a valuable waste for biofuel production yielding up to 270 L/tones, or if pretreated by enzymatic hydrolysis, could generate up to 400 L/tones ethanol (Corbin et al., 2015). *Kluyveromyces marxianus* Y885, effectively degraded the cell wall polymers of GM substrate, secreting enzymes including endopolygalacturonase and producing 10 g/l ethanol and 7.7 g/l glycerol (Williams et al., 2019). In addition, a zero-waste process has been developed to convert GM into solid biofuel, tartaric acid, and concentrated grape extract, which can be utilized in the production of

industrial baker's yeast (Lisićar Vukušić et al., 2023).

Grape marc genetically modified, pretreated with both alkaline and acidic solutions, and enzymatically hydrolyzed, was fermented by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* within a biorefinery scheme. This process produced bio-based succinic acid and a phenolic-rich extract with antioxidant properties, as well as bacterial cellulose, oil, ethanol, crude tannin extract, tartaric acid (Filippi et al., 2021). Lactic acid fermentation of GM with *Lactobacillus plantarum* has been used to produce anti-allergic substances (Tominaga et al., 2010). Additionally, GM has served as a substrate for *L. pentosus*, *L. acidophilus*, and *Debaryomyces hansenii*, leading to the production of valuable compounds such as lactic acid, xylitol, biosurfactants, and bioemulsifiers (Portilla et al., 2010; Portilla et al., 2009; Portilla et al., 2008; Portilla et al., 2007). To produce optical pure L-lactic acid from GM a mutant strain of *L. plantarum* with deletion of the D-lactate synthesis gene was developed (Shen et al., 2023).

The GM fermentation using *L. plantarum*, *Lactobacillus paracasei*, and *Bifidobacterium breve*, resulted promising approach to produce a functional ingredient with antioxidant properties (Campanella et al., 2017). The upcycling of GM through sourdough fermentation using LAB has shown promising applications as a functional ingredient, benefitting from its phenolic compounds, antioxidant activity, and anti-inflammatory potential (Torreggiani et al., 2023). In addition, fermentation of GM with the kombucha consortium (*Gluconoacetobacter*, *Gluconobacter*, *Komagataeibacter*, *Brettanomyces*, and *Schizosaccharomyces*), produced a new functional beverage with strong antioxidant potential, and high antidiabetic and anti-inflammatory activities, providing a promising way to valorize GM (Barakat et al., 2024).

Bacillus subtilis natto proved to be a good producer of cellulase recovered from the GM hydrolysate (Kurt and Cekmecelioglu, 2023). *Burkholderia thailandensis* E264, in mineral salts medium supplemented with GM as sole carbon and energy source, was able to produce long-chain rhamnolipids (up to 13.37 mg/g GM) (Chebbi et al., 2021). Multiple forms of polygalacturonase were produced cultivating *Geotrichum candidum* in GM under SSF (Illková et al., 2012). The reducing sugars obtained from the hydrolysis of cellulose and hemicellulose in GM are utilized to cultivate *Clostridium beijerinckii* for the production of oil, polyphenols, butanol, acetone, and ethanol. This integrated approach efficiently yields valuable biofuels (Jin et al., 2018). Both fresh and the ensiled grape marc with eight strains of LAB, were converted to ethanol via *Escherichia coli* fermentation (Zheng et al., 2012). Fermentation of GM by *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* and *Halomonas* strains can yield biomaterials (Altan Kamer et al., 2021; Joulak et al., 2022). From GM fermentation by *Burkholderia cepacia* (CCM 2656) and *Aspergillus niger* (ATCC 16888), under combined solid-state enzymatic hydrolysis and solid-state fermentation, are produced polyhydroxyalkanoates (biodegradable bioplastics) (Martinez-Avila et al., 2021).

4.3.1.4. Enzymatic hydrolysis. Pectin oligosaccharides with prebiotic potential were extracted from GM through controlled enzymatic hydrolysis (Kokkinomagoulos and Kandyliis, 2023). Using commercial enzyme preparations (viscozyme L and pectinase), and microwave-assisted extraction, were extracted pectin from GM and converted into bioactive pectin-oligosaccharides for food, antimicrobial, and plant biostimulant applications (Cano-Gonzalez et al., 2024). GM protein isolate was hydrolysed by alcalase, flavourzyme and protease either individually or in combination to produce hydrolysates with antihypertensive and antimicrobial properties (Knuf et al., 2025). Cellulase-assisted extraction followed by pressurized liquid extraction enhanced the recovery of phenolic compounds (myricetin, *trans*-caftaric acid, gallic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, epicatechin, epicatechin gallate, and procyanidin B1 and B2) in GM (Machado and Domínguez-Perles, 2017). Phenolic compounds extracted from GM optimized via response surface methodology for temperature, pH, and enzymes (pectinase, cellulase, and tannase), resulted in increased phenolic yield by 66 % and

antioxidant capacity by 80 %. Additionally, tannase facilitated the release of gallic acid, while cellulase aided the release of p-coumaric acid and malvidin-3-O-glucoside (Meini et al., 2019).

4.3.2. Valorization of GM by thermal conversion processes

Grape marc is potentially suitable for the thermal treatments such as combustion, gasification, pyrolysis, torrefaction and hydrothermal carbonization (HCT) (Abreu et al., 2024). GM has been evaluated for pellet production (Oliveira et al., 2024), and its energetic potential is promising for full-scale applications, supporting the feasibility of using GM as a source of energy for agro-industrial activities (Madadian et al., 2022). The valorization of GM has been examined through solid-liquid extraction followed by pyrolysis, and the impact of phenol extraction on GM thermal conversion has also been assessed (Almeida et al., 2022). The char produced from GM through pyrolysis is of significant interest as an adsorbent material. Several studies have aimed at recovering adsorbent materials for Additionally, GM converted into biochar (Martínez-Gómez et al., 2023) has been specifically tested for its effectiveness in removing heavy metals and pesticides residues (Díaz-Ramírez et al., 2021; Yoon et al., 2021).

The recirculation of char from biomass gasification has been studied using dealcoholized GM, both pure and mixed with char produced after the gasification of the feedstock (Hernández et al., 2020). Solar gasification of GM is proposed for syngas production, and practical aspects for industrialization have been addressed (Leiva Butti et al., 2020). The exhausted GM produced in distilleries has valuable energetic properties, particularly in the development of bio-oils and bio-chars (Ibn Ferjani et al., 2020, 2019). Simulations have been used to evaluate hydrogen production from GM gasification, recovered as an energy source (Garrido et al., 2024). The combustion of biogas generated by GM could generate 1520 GWh/y of heat and 1245 GWh/y of electricity, which could be used by wine cellar facilities (Da Ros et al., 2016).

The effects of HTC on the steam gasification were studied in GM, showing its potential to reduce tar formation by removing low-quality volatile compounds (Salaudeen et al., 2021). GM and walnut shells were investigated for a single biomass-to-water ratio, resulting in the production of gases and carbonaceous materials known as hydrochar (Garrido et al., 2021). The efficiency of pyrolysis and torrefaction converting GM into oils, acetic acid, and phenols was evaluated (Del Pozo et al., 2021). Finally, the electricity generation in membrane-less microbial fuel cell using GM was evaluated as an environmentally friendly energy source (Taşkan, 2021).

4.3.3. Valorization of GM by physico-chemical conversion processes

Several researchers have maximized the yield of value-added compounds recovered from GM, positioning it as an alternative, cost-effective source for food, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, and the cosmetic industry (Abreu et al., 2024; Hoss et al., 2021; Kalli et al., 2018). These recovered high-value compounds are utilized to add value to production as nutraceuticals or functional foods with positive health effects (Caponio et al., 2023).

Green extraction methods, such as supercritical fluid extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, pressurized liquid extraction, and ultrasound-assisted extraction, have been designed and optimized to recover phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, fibers, proteins, and more (Aresta et al., 2020; Cañadas et al., 2024; Castro et al., 2024; Da Porto et al., 2022; Garrido et al., 2019; Marianne et al., 2024; Moro et al., 2021; Neto et al., 2021; Silva et al., 2024). Non-ionic surfactants-mediated green extraction has also been investigated for recovering polyphenols (Atanacković Krstonošić et al., 2023; Szadanić et al., 2023). Supercritical CO₂ can assist in fractionating GM, providing a greener alternative for the process (Pedras et al., 2020). A new integrated process has been proposed to fully explore GM for biochemical production, as well as the recovery of oil and phenolic compounds, using pressurized liquid extraction (Jin et al., 2018).

Antioxidants are obtained from GM through isothermal

autohydrolysis, and by using nanofiltration membranes (Mejia et al., 2020). GM has been subjected to extraction/hydrolysis with subcritical water in a semi-continuous reactor, which allows the recovery of phenolic-rich extracts and less rich in carbohydrates. Additionally, GM has been used for the extraction of oleanolic acid, a natural triterpenoid with antidiabetic properties (Errichiello et al., 2024, 2023). GM has also been used for the production of hexanoic acid, which was further converted to ethyl hexanoate, a potential alternative to fossil-derived hexanoic acid (D'Ambrosio et al., 2023). The recovery and stabilization of anthocyanins from GM were achieved by applying eutectic solvents and stabilizing agents (De Souza Mesquita et al., 2023) and ultrasound resulting in enhanced levels compared to conventional processes.

The extraction of condensed tannins from GM, using a mixture of water and sodium hydroxide at 120 °C, has displayed promising properties for use as wood adhesives (Ping et al., 2011). Soluble sugars are extracted from GM using organosolv pretreatment with 85 % v/v ethanol, carried out at 50 °C for 30 min (Jin et al., 2019). Finally, pectin from GM has been extracted using various techniques, including conventional, microwave-assisted and pulsed ultrasound-assisted extraction methods (Spinei and Oroian, 2023).

4.3.4. Other valorization approaches for GM

Some studies propose the direct use of GM without a previous extraction process, for a more complete reutilization of GM. GM powder or flour and seasoning are applied in cereal products bread (Subiria-Cueto et al., 2025), wheat flour and bakery snacks (Alshawi, 2024), chicken breasts and burgers (Gomez et al., 2024), fruit fillings (Saberi et al., 2024), semolina fresh pasta (Liberatore et al., 2025) and more. This approach enables intense fortification with fiber, minerals, protein, oil, phenolic compounds and other constituents of GM, providing enhanced nutritional profile, and sensory properties.

The gelatin/zein nanofiber films with antioxidant properties due to addition of GM (0–20 %) was proposed as promising package material for preserving food quality (Yilmaz et al., 2024). Bio-pesticide derived from GM was developed by inclusion of GM phytochemicals (volatile, fatty acid methyl esters and flavanone non-volatile) oil phase into designer yeast bio-capsule-producing nanocapsules, via emulsification into water phase containing yeast under high-shear mixing, with enhanced pesticide performance (Kala et al., 2024).

GM can be effectively repurposed as a low-cost bio-based adsorbents with potential for practical applications in waste water clean-up activities, acting as biosorbents of heavy metals removal from wastewater (Ungureanu et al., 2022). GM has been proposed as an additive to clay used in the construction of bricks (Crespo-López et al., 2023). In addition, the bio-based polymers from GM are proposed as natural reinforcing fillers (Nanni et al., 2021).

Table 3 presents a summary of value-added compounds and products derived from the valorization of GM, highlighting its potential beyond traditional uses.

5. Perspectives on grape marc valorization for bio-based innovations

Agricultural and agrifood industry residues, particularly from the wine and distillery sectors, hold significant potential for reintegration into new production systems through biorefinery processes and circular bioeconomy (CBE) principles (del Contreras et al., 2022). Although these resources are associated with significant complexity (due to their diversity and variability), technical solutions are available to provide numerous innovative solutions and alternatives to generate end products.

Following the biorefinery concept (Fig. 3), the solid lignocellulosic material of GM can be explored as a fermentative substrate, enabling comprehensive utilization through fractionation and recovery of all its components—carbohydrates, sugars, cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin,

Table 3
Value added compounds and products derived from grape marc valorization.

Valorization approach	Value-added compounds or products derived	Reference
Animal feeding	feed for dairy cattle, Holstein cows, beef heifers, goat, and rabbit feed for broiler chickens feed for Tan lambs feed for piglets and Finishing pigs	(Hixson et al., 2018; Ianni and Martino, 2020; Renna et al., 2023; Scuderi et al., 2019; Vinyard et al., 2021) (Ebrahimzadeh et al., 2018) (Cheng et al., 2023; Massaro Junior et al., 2021) (Kafantaris et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2023) (Mpanga et al., 2023)
Fertilizer	fertilizer applied to maize, wheat, and grape	
Distillation	spirits (Grappa, Zivania, Eau de Vie de, Bagaçeira, Orujo, Tspouro), wine alcohol, liquors, liqueurs, piquette	(Cisneros-Yupanqui et al., 2023; Giannetti et al., 2019; Kokoti et al., 2023; Tsapou et al., 2024; Watrelot and Hollis, 2024) (Doni et al., 2024; Echeverria-Vega et al., 2024; Gabur et al., 2024; Gómez-Brandón et al., 2023, 2022, 2021, 2020; Hanc et al., 2019; Nogales et al., 2020; Troncozo et al., 2024; Villena et al., 2018)
Composting, vermicomposting	plant substrates, soil amendments, bio-fertilizer	
Anaerobic digestion	digestate, biogas, biomethane	(Bordiga et al., 2019; Cáceres et al., 2012; Hungria et al., 2021; Javier et al., 2019; Labartino et al., 2019)
Solid-state and submerged fermentation	bioactive compounds, phenolic compounds, gallic acid, antioxidants, extracts with prebiotic activities, sterols, tannins, flavonoids oil, γ -linolenic acid, carotenoids, fatty acids, bioemulsifiers acetone, butanol, ethanol, bioethanol, biofuel, xylitol, gellan gum tartaric acid, bio-based succinic acid, lactic acid, citric acid cellulose, reducing sugars, exopolysaccharide minerals laccase, endoglucanase, glucanase, tannase, pectinase, α amylase, polygalacturonase, carboxymethyl cellulase, xylanase, cellulase mushroom production, protein-polysaccharide mycelium (proposed for food and feed added-value products or functional ingredient), protein rich animal feed yeast biomass, baker's yeast biopreservation compounds, biocontrol agent, anti-allergic substances biosurfactants, biomaterials, biopolymers, bioplastics	(Jin et al., 2018; Meini et al., 2021, 2020; Mokoichinski et al., 2015; Papadaki et al., 2019; Šelo et al., 2024, 2023a, 2023b; Siller-Sánchez et al., 2024; Teles et al., 2019; Yildirim and Sā-Zmen, 2021) (Chebbi et al., 2021; Dulf et al., 2020; Jin et al., 2018; Mokoichinski et al., 2015; Portilla et al., 2010) (Altan Kamer et al., 2021; Corbin et al., 2015; Jin et al., 2018; Lisicar Vukusić et al., 2023; Rodríguez et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2012) (Başgmez, 2021; Filippi et al., 2022, 2021) (Filippi et al., 2022; Joulak et al., 2022) (Portilla et al., 2009) (Cabezudo et al., 2023; Corrêa et al., 2024; Illková et al., 2012; Meini et al., 2020; Šelo et al., 2021; Teles et al., 2019)

Table 3 (continued)

Valorization approach	Value-added compounds or products derived	Reference
		(Campanella et al., 2017; Cebrián et al., 2024; Hasanzadeh et al., 2023; Kachrimanidou et al., 2023b, 2023c; Rybicka et al., 2024; Torreggiani et al., 2023)
		(Lisicar Vukusić et al., 2023; Lo Curto, 2001) (Bai et al., 2008; Mewa-Ngongang et al., 2019; Tominaga et al., 2010) (Joulak et al., 2022; Martinez-Avila et al., 2021; Nanni et al., 2021; Portilla et al., 2007)
Combustion, gasification, pyrolysis, torrefaction	pellets	(Abreu et al., 2024; Madadian et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2024)
hydrothermal carbonization	char (used as adsorbent materials for removing heavy metals and pesticides), biochar (used as absorbent for removing pesticide residues), charcoal, hydrochar bio-oils, bio-fuel (renewable energy)	(Diaz-Ramirez et al., 2021; Garrido et al., 2021; Hernández et al., 2020; Martínez-Gómez et al., 2023; Yoon et al., 2021) (Garrido et al., 2024; Leiva Butti et al., 2020; Tamešová et al., 2021; Taşkan, 2021)
	syngas, hydrogen	(Ibn Ferjani et al., 2020, 2019)
Extraction	phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, fibers, proteins oil, antioxidant, oleanolic acid, hexanoic acid, condensed tannins, soluble sugars, pectin, volatile organic compounds, resveratrol	(Aresta et al., 2020; Atanacković Krstonošić et al., 2023; Cañadas et al., 2024; Castro et al., 2024; Da Porto et al., 2022; D'Ambrosio et al., 2023; De Souza Mesquita et al., 2023; Errichiello et al., 2024, 2023; Garrido et al., 2019; Jin et al., 2019, 2018; Marianne et al., 2024; Moro et al., 2021; Neto et al., 2021; Pedras et al., 2020; Sazdanić et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2024)
Nanofiltration membranes	antioxidants	(Caponio et al., 2023; Mejia et al., 2020)
Enzymatic hydrolysis	pectin oligosaccharides (prebiotics), peptides	(Knuf et al., 2025)
Other valorization approaches	grape marc flour or powder as food fortifier, seasoning construct bricks adhesive for wood particle boards biodegradable, aktive packaging materials biosorbent (for removing of emergent contaminants, Pb from wastewater and mycotixins from liquid media) bio-pesticide	(Alshawi, 2024; Gomez et al., 2024; Liberatore et al., 2025; Saberi et al., 2024; Subiria-Cueto et al., 2025) (Crespo-López et al., 2023) (Ping et al., 2011) (Yilmaz et al., 2024) (Gubitoso et al., 2023; Ungureanu et al., 2022)
		(Kala et al., 2024)

and bioactive compounds. This approach facilitates the production of multiple bio-based products and components. GM is a promising candidate for bioconversion and valorization via microbial fermentation, yielding a wide range of valuable products, including nutrient-rich

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of grape marc bioconversion into value-added products in fungal-based biorefinery.

food and animal feed, bio-based succinic acid, biocontrol agent, bioemulsifiers, bioethanol, biofuel, biopreservation compounds, biosurfactants, renewable energy, industrial enzymes, and other bioactive compounds (Ilyas et al., 2021; Rani and Indrajeet, 2020).

Recent research has investigated fungal degradation of grape marc's lignocellulosic biomass, yet its potential in submerged fermentation through edible filamentous fungi for sustainable production of novel protein sources. Indeed, bioconversion of GM has been investigated using filamentous fungi (e.g., *A. elegans*, *A. awamori*, *A. niger*, *P. chrysosporium*, *R. oryzae*, *T. asperellum*, *T. reesei*, *T. virde*, and *U. isabelline*) as well as other microorganisms (e.g., *S. cerevisiae*, *A. succinogenes*, *B. subtilis natto*, *C. beijerinckii*, *L. acidophilus*, *L. pentosus*, *L. plantarum*, *S. paucimobilis*, etc.). Filamentous fungi, particularly *Aspergillus* and *Trichoderma* species, have shown remarkable potential in converting winery waste into value-added products, mainly through SSF (Zepf and Jin, 2013). However, the production of microbial protein-rich biomass from GM for food and feed application remain largely underexplored.

Considering the GM composition and its various valorization pathways explored to date, an interesting and viable approach involves its bioconversion through submerged and/or solid-state fermentation using edible filamentous fungi. The primary goal of GM bioconversion via fungal fermentation is to produce sustainable, high-quality alternative proteins, contributing to food and feed innovation, enhancing food security, promoting healthy diets, and supporting the transition to sustainable food production systems.

The fungal biorefinery approach for GM valorization, as illustrated in Fig. 3, outlines an innovative and sustainable method for converting winery and distillery by-products into high-value bioproducts. Grape marc, a lignocellulosic-rich residue, after appropriate pre-treatment processes for enhancing its suitability for fungal cultivation, is followed by edible filamentous fungi inoculation and cultivation under controlled submerged fermentation conditions. During fungal fermentation, a broad spectrum of bioactive and industrially relevant compounds can be synthesized, including bioethanol, organic acids, and several enzymes like cellulases, laccases, and proteases—each holding significant applications in food, feed, textile, and bioenergy industries.

Upon completion of the fermentation process, downstream processing will enable the recovery of secondary metabolites and natural biocolorants from the liquid fraction (broth). Additionally, this fraction can

be further refined for use in the production of biofertilizers, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices.

Simultaneously, the fungal biomass is separated, and processed to obtain mycoprotein—a nutrient-rich microbial protein source, rich in essential amino acids, dietary fiber, fatty acids, and bioactive compounds, making it an attractive alternative protein source for both human and animal nutrition. In addition, this new protein source could be effectively used as a food ingredient, offering potential for developing functional foods and meat substitutes, aligning with growing demands for sustainable and health-oriented diets.

6. Conclusions

The wine and distillery industries, like all agri-food industries, generate significant amounts of organic waste in the form of byproducts that are considered potential resources for valorization. Grape marc is a prominent example—this high-volume, low-cost and underutilized by-product is a strong candidate for integration into biorefinery frameworks and circular economies. Addressing the waste management challenges associated with grape marc from wineries and distilleries requires a strategic shift towards circular economy principles and innovative valorization approaches.

In this review, the main solid waste stream from the wine and distillery industry was assessed in terms of its abundance and chemical composition. In line with sustainable development goals and circular bioeconomy strategies, the review confirms that grape marc is not merely an agricultural residue but a rich bioresource capable of generating a wide array of high-value bio-based products. This study highlights the unique versatility of grape marc and its potential applications across various sectors, including food and feed, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, fuel and energy, construction, and soil conditioning, among others.

Through a critical analysis of traditional and emerging technologies—including biological, thermal, and chemical conversion methods—this study reveals a clear path toward more promising pathways for sustainable and circular production systems. Particularly, the integration of grape marc in a fungal biorefinery system is identified as a transformative approach. This system offers an eco-efficient and sustainable route for producing a wide array of cost-effective,

environmentally friendly, and valuable products. Notably, the production of protein-rich biomass from filamentous fungi grown on grape marc presents a highly promising valorization pathway. In addition, this strategy enables the production of relevant enzymes, bioactive compounds, and other metabolites, aligning with circular bioeconomy principles and the EU's zero-waste targets. This forward-looking perspective offers actionable insights into how grape marc valorization can drive innovation, investment, and sustainability across the European food and bioeconomy landscape.

However, several limitations remain. The heterogeneity of grape marc—arising from differences in grape variety, vinification methods, and regional practices—poses challenges for standardization and scalability of biorefinery approaches. Furthermore, most current research is limited to laboratory and pilot-scale experiments, with a lack of data on long-term environmental, economic, and operational feasibility at industrial scale. Future research should focus on (i) optimizing pre-treatment and conversion processes for different types of grape marc; (ii) evaluating the environmental and socio-economic impacts of large-scale implementation; (iii) developing cost-effective downstream processing techniques for fungal bioproducts; and (iv) exploring synergistic models that integrate grape marc valorization with other agri-food waste streams in multi-feedstock biorefineries.

This review paper not only underscores grape marc's potential as a key feedstock in the bioeconomy but also lays the groundwork for advancing sustainable, circular, and innovation-driven solutions within the wine industry and beyond, advocating the grape marc's integral role in sustainable food systems and circular bioeconomy goals. Moreover, this paper can make a significant contribution to the scientific community by laying a foundation for future scientific exploration of potential bio-based products from grape marc. Additionally, it can serve as practical guidance for stakeholders in the wine and distillery industries, outlining how they can shift toward integrated, value-driven upcycling strategies into high-value products, helping the sector to reduce environmental impact while generating new economic opportunities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luziana Hoxha: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad J. Taherzadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Matteo Marangon:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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